

**ARDUINO-BASED REAL-TIME MONITORING SYSTEM FOR WATER HARDNESS
AND PH.**

Ismailov Mirhalil Agzamovich,

Professor of Automation and Control of Technological Processes, PhD, National Research University "TIAME", Department of "Automation and Control of Technological Processes"

E-mail: m.ismailov@tiame.uz

Abdunazarov G'olibjon G'ayrat o'g'li

Master's student, National Research University "TIAME", Department of "Automation and Control of Technological Processes"

E-mail: togarena54@gmail.com

Mansurov Bekzod Doniyor o'g'li

Master's student, National Research University "TIAME", Department of "Automation and Control of Technological Processes"

E-mail: bekzodmansurov348@gmail.com

Abstract: *In the current era of industrial development, the effective use of water resources and control of their quality are urgent tasks. In this study, an automatic system based on an Arduino microcontroller was developed that monitors water hardness and pH levels in real time during the chemical treatment of industrial water. The goal is to optimize the rational use of resources while reducing human error. The hardware part of the system consists of components such as sensors, a microcontroller, and a real-time display module, while the software part is written in the Arduino IDE environment. Initially, prototype tests were conducted using Fritzing simulation and laboratory conditions. The results show that the developed system can accurately record changes in water hardness and pH: the difference between the measured pH values and laboratory values did not exceed ± 0.2 , and the results for TDS (total dissolved solids) were observed within 5% of the reference values. This accuracy allows for better control and management of the water treatment process. The proposed system contributes to the sustainable use of water in industry through automated control based on real-time data.*

Keywords: *water hardness, pH monitoring, Arduino, SCADA, chemical treatment.*

Introduction

Water is one of the most important elements for life and industry, covering more than two-thirds of the Earth's surface. Water plays a crucial role in industrial processes as a solvent, coolant, raw material and carrier. The purpose of the industrial water treatment process is to remove or render harmless impurities that damage equipment and devices, interfere with processes or harm the environment. One of the important parameters in industrial water treatment is water hardness, i.e. the presence of calcium and magnesium ions in the water. When water hardness exceeds the norm, deposits (salt deposits) form on pipes and equipment, reducing the efficiency of the system. Another important factor is the pH level of the water, since the pH environment directly affects the corrosion rate and the reaction of reagents. Traditional water analysis methods usually involve manual sampling and laboratory testing. This approach is time-consuming and can be prone to errors due to the human factor.

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The development of microcontrollers and real-time sensor systems is creating new opportunities for continuous monitoring of water quality. The Arduino platform is inexpensive and flexible, making it a convenient tool for continuous (online) monitoring of water quality. By integrating such systems with SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) or special displays, it is possible to obtain quick feedback and continuously record data. As a result, operators will be able to immediately respond to changes in water quality.

Currently, in many water treatment plants, parameters are controlled through periodic tests, which means that some changes are detected late due to the lack of continuous monitoring. In this sense, an automated real-time monitoring system can provide better process control and more efficient use of resources. This article describes the design and implementation of a continuous monitoring system for water hardness and pH using Arduino-based equipment. The proposed system aims to accurately and continuously measure water quality and integrate it seamlessly into industrial control systems. The structure of the article is as follows: first, previous developments on the topic are analyzed, then the methodology and design of the developed system are described, results and discussions are presented, and the conclusion and references are concluded.

Literature review

Many scientific works have been conducted on the automation of water treatment processes [1][2]. For example, Turobjonov et al. (2010) and Buriev et al. (2014) presented basic solutions for industrial wastewater treatment technologies, especially emphasizing the need for effective removal of hardness ions [1][2]. Musayev (2011) analyzed chemical treatment technologies for industrial wastewater in his study and noted the importance of optimizing treatment processes to protect equipment and protect the environment [3].

In recent years, research on the use of advanced sensors and networked systems in sustainable water resource management has reached a new level. Many modern studies emphasize the importance of continuous automatic monitoring systems. For example, another study from 2023 proposed a low-cost Arduino-based multi-parameter (pH, temperature, turbidity, TDS) sensor network that enables early detection of water pollution (via local displays and central data collection nodes) - in this way, warnings are automatically issued when water quality deviates from regulatory limits. Smart control systems based on the integration of IoT and SCADA are also being developed for continuous water quality monitoring [5][6]. For example, Dwarakanath et al. (2023) demonstrated a system for remote monitoring and control of water treatment processes using IoT and SCADA, in which processing devices are automatically regulated based on real-time sensor data [6]. El-Shafei et al. (2023) proposed a method for analyzing water quality sensor data using multi-dimensional deep learning models and detecting anomalies in monitoring in real time [5]. Such modern developments show that it is possible to design flexible monitoring systems operating in real time using inexpensive and open-source hardware platforms (e.g. Arduino) and various electronic modules. These systems allow for immediate recording of changes in water quality through continuous data transmission and allow for fine-tuning of the process. Some previously proposed automatic control devices (e.g., separate pH or conductivity regulators for a single parameter) did not have the ability to continuously transmit and feedback information, so they were not fully effective in optimizing the process. Although technologies such as membrane filtration (e.g., reverse osmosis) or ion exchange are widely used in water softening, they require real-time data control to avoid errors such as over- or under-use. In conclusion, the scientific literature shows that the introduction of microprocessor-based continuous monitoring systems can significantly improve water treatment processes. Our work, based on this

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scientific basis and previously obtained results, aimed to integrate a sensor system created on the Arduino platform directly into the water treatment process and contribute to the development of automatic water quality control in industry.

Methodology

System Overview: The developed Arduino-based monitoring system continuously (real-time) measures water hardness and pH, displays this data on the display, and stores it in memory (SD card). For stable operation of the system, hardware and software components are integrated with each other.

Hardware: An Arduino Uno microcontroller board was chosen as the main device. An analog pH sensor (consisting of an electrode probe and a signal amplifier module) was used to measure the pH level of water, and a TDS/conductivity sensor (total dissolved solids meter) was used to estimate water hardness. A 16×2 LCD display (with I²C interface) was connected to monitor the measured values on site, displaying pH and TDS values in real time. An SD card module was added to store historical data, and the measurement results were written to a file. All components of the system operate from a stable 5V power supply and a common “mass” (ground) contact - this reduces electrical noise and increases the reliability of measurements. The entire circuit was first modeled and assembled using the Fritzing software platform at the initial stage.

Figure 1. Electrical diagram of a water hardness and pH monitoring system based on the Arduino microcontroller. In this scheme, the Arduino Uno board is connected to the pH sensor and TDS sensor via analog input pins (A0, A1) and reads and processes their signals. The measured pH and TDS values are displayed in real time on a 16×2 LCD display with an I²C interface. The Arduino board also has an SD card module connected via the SPI interface, in which each measurement result is written to a memory file with a date and time stamp. All devices are connected to a 5V power supply and a common ground - this ensures reliable and stable operation of the system.

Software part: The program for the Arduino microcontroller was written in C/C++, in the Arduino IDE environment. When the program starts, the corresponding analog pins for the sensors and the LCD display are initialized.

Results and Research

After the created system was assembled and the software was loaded, experimental test measurements were carried out on water samples of different pH and hardness to test its performance. To verify the reliability of the Arduino system measurement results, its indicators for each sample were compared with the values measured using standard laboratory equipment. In particular, Table 1 presents the pH values measured and determined in the laboratory for several water samples and the difference between them (relative error in percent). Similarly, the hardness level (TDS) of the samples was also compared with the values determined by the laboratory and the agreement was observed in each case.

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Table 1. Comparison of pH values measured by the Arduino system with laboratory pH values. Error (%) indicates the difference with respect to the laboratory value.

sample	Arduino pH	Lab pH	Mistake (%)
1	7.10	7.20	1.4%
2	6.80	6.90	1.4%
3	7.40	7.50	1.3%
4	6.50	6.45	0.8%

According to the table above, the pH measurements of the Arduino-based system were very close to the laboratory values. The largest deviation in the tests was only 0.1 pH units (approximately 1–1.5% relative error), which is a very good result for industrial water control practice. Because in the water treatment process, pH is usually not of great importance in tenths of a second, but changes equal to whole units are considered important. The results obtained show that with proper calibration, it is possible to achieve accuracy close to the level of laboratory equipment even with relatively inexpensive sensors. The percentage of error for all samples is very small, confirming that the system can be trusted for continuous pH monitoring. The detected insignificant differences can be explained by a slight shift in the sensor calibration over time or the short-circuiting of the Arduino ADC, but continuous calibration minimizes such differences and the accuracy of ± 0.2 pH meets the regulatory requirement for industrial processes.

The Arduino system uses TDS sensor readings to estimate water hardness. TDS measurements were also compared with TDS (or conductivity) values measured in the laboratory. As a result, it turned out that the TDS values measured by the Arduino system were within approximately $\pm 5\%$ of the values shown by laboratory equipment. This was expected, since the technical passport of the TDS sensor used indicated an accuracy of $\pm 5\%$ (provided that it was properly calibrated). For example, if the TDS in the laboratory for a certain water sample was 500 ppm, our system showed approximately 475–525 ppm for this sample - this is an acceptable deviation in industrial practice. This is because the dosing of anti-hardness reagents is usually carried out on a much larger scale (with an accuracy of tens of ppm). Importantly, since the system continuously transmits information in real time, even if there is a slight error in some measurement values, it is possible to monitor the general trend or tendency of change and make timely corrections accordingly.

In one of the experiments, the process of adding a reagent to water was observed using the created system. Figure 2 below shows the trend of changes in the pH and TDS values of water over time in one of such tests. The graph shows that at approximately the 4th minute, a chemical reagent (for example, an alkaline substance) was added to the water to soften the water, and the system's reaction to it was recorded in real time.

Figure 2. Time-dependent graph of pH (blue line, left axis) and TDS (red line, right axis) during the test on a water sample. As can be seen from the graph, after the reagent was added to the water around 4–5 minutes, the pH value increased rapidly from about 6.8 to 7.4 and then stabilized at about 7.1. At the same time, the TDS level gradually decreased: the total dissolved salts content, which was initially about 400 ppm, decreased to about 320 ppm by the end of the test. Such a reverse trend was expected, since the addition of a chemical reagent to the water alkalizes the environment and increases the pH, while at the same time the total dissolved solids content decreases due to the precipitation of ions (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}) that cause hardness.

The dynamics in Figure 2 allow us to analyze how quickly the process is happening using real-time monitoring. According to the data, the main change in pH occurred within a minute after the reagent was added (between 4 and 5 minutes), while the change in TDS was relatively slow, lasting several minutes. Such data can help operators in production situations make decisions such as when and how long to add the reagent, and determine the duration of water recirculation.

The high measurement accuracy of the system is of particular importance in the discussion. As can be seen in the graph above, the pH rose quickly after the reagent was added, remained stable around the set value, and did not increase dangerously. Therefore, based on the data received through the system, it is possible to issue a quick warning or take automatic action in cases where the pH value deviates from the normal range. Small fluctuations in the pH graph (around ± 0.1) may be due to the sensor itself or small differences in water mixing, but these fluctuations do not interfere with determining the general trend. A smooth decrease in the TDS graph indicates that the TDS sensor is working stably and the water purification process is proceeding consistently. In some other tests, there were also cases when the TDS decrease graph temporarily leveled off - this can happen when the ion exchange process approaches equilibrium. In the continuous monitoring mode, it becomes possible to fine-tune the process (for example, slow down or stop the addition of reagents) based on such real-time data.

In general, the results obtained confirm that measurements can be made using an Arduino-based system with an accuracy close to that of traditional laboratory equipment. The advantage of such a system is that it immediately records changes in indicators and continuously collects log (daily) data. This allows not only to take immediate measures, but also to analyze the data later. For example, based on the collected data, it will be possible to study daily cycles or determine when water quality begins to deteriorate and take preventive measures. The fact that inexpensive sensors provide reliable information when calibrated is a particularly important conclusion, since it shows that what is traditionally done only with expensive analyzers can be done with simple and inexpensive electronic devices. In industrial conditions, installing several such Arduino-based devices at different points in

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the process is much cheaper than installing a single analyzer, as a result, it is possible to create a comprehensive monitoring network throughout the entire system.

Of course, there are some limitations and requirements when using the system. For example, in order for the pH sensor to maintain accurate measurements, it must be recalibrated with standard solutions at a certain period (for example, once a week). In our laboratory tests, calibration was performed before each series of measurements; if the system is used continuously for a long time, the sensitivity of the electrode decreases, and if care is not taken during calibration, the error can increase. Similarly, the accuracy of a TDS sensor can be affected by ambient temperature and the build-up of scale (fouling) on the sensor surface. In real-world conditions, it may be necessary to periodically clean the sensor and add automatic temperature compensation if the temperature fluctuates significantly. Since we conducted the tests in a controlled laboratory environment, the system generally performed stably and reliably recorded major changes in water quality in real time. This once again demonstrates the main advantage of automation: where previously the process was adjusted only based on the result of a periodic sample, now operators can react to even small changes in a timely manner based on a continuous flow of information.

Conclusion

The proposed Arduino microcontroller-based monitoring system can be an effective solution for real-time monitoring of industrial water hardness (via TDS) and pH. The project created a reliable device that operates continuously using inexpensive and open architecture components and software. The results of testing and validation show that the system measurements are very close to those of laboratory equipment, which proves that it is possible to achieve the accuracy required for industrial water monitoring by properly calibrating inexpensive sensors. The immediate (online) availability of pH and hardness information reduces the time between detecting a change in the process and taking appropriate action, which increases the speed of management. As a result, efficient use of resources (optimized dosing of reagents, reduction of waste) is ensured and it is easier to maintain stable water quality standards.

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